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ONLINE SHOPPING TRENDS OF VIETNAMESE YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

With the drastic development of the Internet and social media, online shopping gradually gains traction after being introduced to the market in the 1990s. Since the outbreak of Covid-19 in 2020, this trend has become more popular on a global scale. There are numerous benefits including the wide range of products, sales, and saving consumers' time, which attract more and more people, especially the youth. As far as the increasing importance of online shopping is concerned, our research team has a deeper insight into it through articles and research on Vietnamese Generation Z, who were born from 1995 to 2012 to understand more about the demands, time usage, advantages, and disadvantages of online shopping. From the results of the research, we put forward some solutions that consumers could implement to purchase things online more effectively.

KEYWORDS

Trends, online shopping, Vietnamese young people

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1. Identify the issue

Since its introduction, online shopping has become an indispensable part of our social life. Nowadays, with a smartphone and a few clicks, consumers can easily shop and have their products delivered to their doorstep without wasting too much time, and effort to shop around for the best choice.

Online shopping has been a buying trend among consumers these days, especially young and busy people. It has many benefits in our daily life where most people encounter a heavy amount of work and studying daily, leaving them no spare time for shopping. However, some negative impacts of it should be taken into consideration

In Vietnam 2020, according to the Ecommerce website, about 31% of citizens used the Internet for 3-5 hours, those using 5-7 hours accounted for 28%, those using 7-9 hours took up 17%, those using more than 9 hours comprised of 11 %, and the figure for under 3 hours is the lowest, 15%. At this time, 43% of people shop at online stores. The results of research with 1078 consumers showed that the figure for online shopping in 2019 was 77% and increased to 88% in 2020 which means that online shopping is more popular with consumers. (Phan Thi Hoi, 2023)

According to online shopping statistics in 2022, free delivery is the main reason why 53% of consumers opt for shopping online because they don't have to spend time and money going to physical shops but just have to wait at home for their products without delivery fees. In addition, there are several causes leading to this trend: discount policy and vouchers (41%), good reviews (35%), exchange and return policy (33%), and payment process (30%). (Ehou.vn, 2023)

However, apart from the advantages of online shopping, it can have imminent negative impacts on consumers. According to the 2021 e-commerce report, consumers have to deal with many problems associated with this trend: prices (44%), low quality (42%), the risk of information leakage (33%), delay in the delivery process (25%)(Ministry of industry and trade, 2017)

This research aims to discover more about the trends in online shopping of young people to answer these questions: What is the intensity of using social media? What is the aim of using social platforms? What e-commerce websites that young people usually refer to for online shopping? How much money do they spend on online shopping every month? What products are regularly purchased? What are the benefits of online shopping? What are the disadvantages of online shopping? What measures can young people take to shop online more effectively?

2. Overview of online shopping

2.1. Definition, and characteristics of online shopping

In some publication research, individuals and organizations have definitions for online shopping:

Online shopping is a way to indirectly purchase products, goods through computers, and the Internet without coming to the seller's stores. Customers have various choices of payment such as ATM card, banking, cash on delivery... (Nguyen Ngoc, 2023)

Online shopping is a form of e-commerce that allows consumers to directly pay for products or services from retailers through the Internet. Customers can find out information about the product by visiting the retailers' website or among other retailers by searching tools, which show the prices of

similar products from different websites. Customers can purchase online using a variety of internet-connected devices, including desktop computers, laptops, tablets, and smartphones. (Wikipedia, 2023)

Online shopping is a form of e-commerce that allows customers to directly purchase goods or services from the seller using a web browser on the internet. Current forms of online shopping such as e-commerce site applications; social networks; selling websites. (Nguyen Thi Minh Ha, 2023)

Online shopping is a form of buying goods online through websites and shopping applications available on phones or the internet. Here, customers can choose and compare prices comfortably without going to the store to see. The payment is also very convenient, you can pay via ATM card, debit card, or Visa card, or you can pay immediately upon receipt. It can be seen that online shopping brings a lot of benefits to users, helping people to optimize their shopping time. (Thuy Tran, 2023)

In summary, online shopping has some outstanding features as follows:

- Customers can shop online by using many different devices connected to the internet such as computers, phones, and tablets.
- When shopping online, customers decide to buy through viewing product images, along with information about characteristics, features, prices, and especially previous buyers' reviews.
- E-commerce platforms often allow shoppers to use search tools to find specific brands or items.

2.2. Advantages and disadvantages of online shopping:

Advantages of online shopping.

Online shopping is convenient for busy consumers but having shopping needs because they can purchase everywhere with a phone. (Duong Thi Thu Huong et al, 2022)

According to Anh Dung's research, along with other convenient gadgets, online shopping provides consumers with the tool to refer to previous buyer reviews of the product on which they intend to purchase and decide whether to buy or not. Besides, after the order, the product will be delivered to their door. (Anh Dung, 2022)

Online shopping not only serves as a way to purchase necessary items but also to help consumers relax and reduce nervous tension. In addition, online shopping can relieve stress and lift feelings when they must stay at home for a long time. (Minh Trang, 2022; Phuong Ha, 2023). Moreover, online shopping is a channel with sales and a diverse range of products.

Disadvantages of online shopping

However, many articles have mentioned the risks of online shopping. Some survey results have shown that online shopping leads to spending quite liberally, especially for young people in Viet Nam. If the product exceeds its income, it leads to the possibility of falling into bad debt when the payment is overdue is very high. Many people, especially young ones, purchase a product just because of its good price not because they truly have needs. Otherwise, the difference between the product received and the advertised image or the disposal of unusable orders can pose a waste and a threat to the environment. (Minh Trang, 2022; Phuong Ha, 2023).

3. Research method

To conduct "Trends in online shopping of Vietnamese young people", the research team utilize 2 main methods including desk research (reviewing published documents in the media, books, and journals) and sociological investigation (collecting answers from Generation Z who was born between 1995 and 2012). The collected data will be assimilated and analyzed by Excell.

Using desk research, the research team reviewed documents on online shopping trends, advantages/disadvantages of online shopping, websites/fan pages that the young generation often chooses... and their characteristics from the research overview, the team surveyed online shopping trends of Vietnamese youth. The survey is designed with a 5-level Likert scale including:

1. Strongly disagree; 2. Disagree; 3. No comments; 4. Agree; 5. Strongly agree.

The sociological investigation method conducted by the research team is based on the convenience sampling method and the "snowball" method - the method of finding the next subject from another subject's suggestion or recommendation. The survey was made on Google Drive and conducted preliminary on 5 people who shop online regularly. The completed survey form was sent to young people through a link:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfajvRx21pV6w4AmSis_nCGAOtI-1FFTQUQ-HgpZ7oYW-rSGQ/viewform through social media platforms: Facebook, Zalo, Email...

The total number of survey questionnaires collected was 299. The survey data was synthesized and statistically analyzed using Excel and SPSS software to evaluate the research issue.

4. Research results

4.1 Characteristics of survey object

Chart 1. Genders of respondents

Source: survey results of the research team

299 people were answering the survey, including 176 women (58.9%), 101 men (33.8%), and 22 people who did not want to be specific (7.4%).

Chart 2. Ages of respondents

Source: survey results of the research team

299 people were answering the survey, including 42 people under 15 years old (14%), 77 people between 15 and 18 years old (26%), 65 people between 18 and 22 years old (22%), and 115 people above 22 years old (38%).

4.2. General information about social media usage

The usage of social media is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Daily use of social media

Level of usage	Number
Non-use	13
Less use	44
Normal use	76
Regular use	99
Frequent use	67

Source: survey results of the research team

Among 299 answering the survey, it can be divided into 5 levels: 1 point is non-use (13 people); 2. Less use (44 people); 3. Normal (76 people); 4. Regular use (99 people); 5. Frequent use. The average score is 3.54, which means that subject surveys use regularly daily. This result is similar to what is published in Anh, N.T.V & et al (2023)

About the time of using social media

Chart 3. Time spent on social media per day.

Source: survey results of the research team

Among 299 respondents, 92 used social media for 3-5 hours (31%), 66 used it for 5-7 hours (22%), 67 used it for 1-3 hours (23%), and 39 used it for 7-9 hours (13). 19 people used it for less than 1 hour (6%), and 16 people used it for more than 9 hours (5%). Therefore, the proportion of respondents who use social media for 3-5 hours per day is the highest.

About the purpose of using social media, Anh. N.T.V & et al (2023)’s results show that people use social media to update information, connect, communicate, learn, and share stories. Mai Hoang Thinh (2023) mentioned entertainment purposes; Duong Thi Thu Huong and Pham Thi Men Thuong (2022) refer to the purpose of information updating, sharing stories, talking, and online shopping. Mai Hoang Thinh (2023) shows the purpose of booking a car, finding information about health care, traveling, or learning about mother and baby information. A summary of the purposes mentioned in the articles, previous studies, and survey articles on the purpose of using social networks shows that

Chart 4. Purposes of using social media

Source: survey results of the research team

The results in Chart 4 show that entertainment purposes accounted for the highest number of respondents (164 people), followed by communication and connection (160 people), information

update (128 people), and studying (112 people). Learning about mother and baby took up the lowest number (38 people).

4.3. Online shopping trend of Vietnamese young people
About the online shopping experience

Chart 5. Online shopping rates

Source: survey results of the research team

The results in Chart 5 show that among 299 respondents, there are 262 people (88%) have shopped online and 37 people (12%) have never shopped online.

Chart 6. Reasons why not shop online

Source: survey results of the research team

Among 37 people who have never shopped online, each had different reasons. The results in Figure 6 show that 16 people do not shop online because they think they may become victims of online fraud and have to wait for delivery; 15 people are afraid of not being able to see the products they are going to buy and 13 people think that the purchase may have been mishandled during delivery.

Chart 7. Intentions of shopping online

Source: survey results of the research team

Among 37 people who have never shopped online, 10 people will shop online in the future, 18 people are considering (49%) and 9 people have never thought of it.

About online shopping behavior:

Chart 8. Online shopping behavior

Source: survey results of the research team

Among 262 people who have experienced online shopping, the results in Chart 9 show that 154 people use Shopee application shopping, followed by 123 people using Facebook, 94 people using Instagram, 90 people using Tiki, and 88 people using Lazada, 73 people used Tiktok, 70 people used Zalo, 68 people used Fanpage, 59 people used YouTube, 46 people used Twitter, 41 people used Sendo, and 5 people used other methods for shopping.

About products when shopping online:

Chart 9. Products when shopping online

Source: survey results of the research team

In terms of items purchased online, the figures in chart 10 show that 131 people shop for clothes; 117 people shop for phone accessories, technology, and electronics, 117 people shop for jewelry, and fashion accessories, 112 people shop for beauty products, 104 shop for fast food, 97 shop for school supplies, 90 people shop for kitchen equipment, home appliances, 75 people shop for medical supplies/health care products, 50 people shop for vouchers/other supplies. In conclusion, shopping for clothes accounts for the largest proportion, followed by phone accessories, technology, electronics, jewelry, fashion accessories... and the number of purchasing vouchers and services accounts for the least.

About money paid for online shopping:

Chart 10. Money spent on online shopping per month

Source: survey results of the research team

Answering the survey, 66 people pay 200,000 VND - 500,000 VND for online shopping, 56 people pay 1,000,000 - 1,500,000 VND, 42 people pay less than 200,000 VND, 40 people pay 500,000-1,000,000 VND, 33 people pay 1,500,000 - 2,000,000 VND and 25 people pay more than 2,000,000 VND.

About payment methods when shopping online:

Chart 11. Payment methods for online shopping

Source: survey results of the research team

When shopping online, customers can use many different payment methods, survey about the payment methods that customers often use, 153 people pay by bank transfer, 152 people pay by cash, 66 people pay by credit card, 62 people pay by e-wallet, 56 people pay via Mobile Banking, 29 people pay by online check, 26 people pay via electronic payment gateway, 1 person pay by other methods.

The results on the benefits and risks of online shopping are shown in charts 12 and 13:

Chart 12. Advantages of online shopping

The results with the average score of statements about the advantages of online shopping showed that 299 survey participants answered "agree" with the statements. Among them, the result recorded the

highest score of 3.97 points with 2 comments "Online products are very diverse " and "Very convenient for busy consumers but have shopping needs". And the statement with the lowest score was "Online shopping is a way to reduce stress".

Chart 13. Disadvantages of online shopping

The survey results with the average score of the statements about the risks of online shopping (Figure 13) showed the highest score of 3.37 points with the statement "Causes a tendency to spend quite liberally". The assessment with the lowest score is "Difference between the product received and the advertised image" with a score of 2.95.

How to shop online effectively:

Surveying about effective online shopping, the results show some ways to help young people shop online effectively:

Chart 14. How to shop online effectively

Source: survey results of the research team

The results in Chart 14 indicate that to effectively shop online, customers should shop from reputable suppliers/websites and refer to previous customers' comments and feedback, while 139 people agree that they need to carefully review product information, size, and cost. 122 people state that before making a purchase decision, multiple reference prices are needed, and customers should actively overcome the feeling of "buying immediately" In addition, 104 agree that people should consult with the sales policy, carefully check before receiving the goods, and retain payment receipts to prove the purchase. Regarding payment methods, 108 say that people should consider payment methods when paying. Regarding additional services, more than 80 people agree that when "free return" services or "free delivery", customers need to resist the urge to purchase more products.

5. Some recommendations to promote online shopping:

Recommendations to customers, especially for Vietnamese young people

The survey results show that to shop online effectively, customers need to choose and buy goods from a reliable supplier/website and should refer to the reviews and feedback of customers who have purchased before. In addition, before deciding to buy, customers should carefully review product information and sales policies; consider that the price will come with the quality, and consult the price of other retailers.

In terms of buying psychology, when shopping online, customers need to control their feelings of wanting to buy impulsively and resist the urge to buy more when there are additional services such as free service, and promotions when buying more....

When deciding to buy, customers should choose an online payment method to involve the Bank in the payment process; check the goods carefully before receiving them and keep the payment receipt as proof of purchase in case of future risks.

Recommendations to online organizations/individuals

To create good business efficiency and effective shopping experience for online consumers, online retailers need to improve their reputation, rather than selling inferior products, and are committed to providing products of the same quality as online advertisements.

In the delivery process, retailers have to pay attention to packaging to ensure transportation safety; strictly control the transportation process to ensure timely delivery.

Strengthen social responsibility and environmental protection awareness to boost image, reputation, and brand, and achieve sustainable development in e-commerce.

Recommendations to the government:

For the government, to limit the unexpected risks or consequences of online shopping, it is necessary to regularly inspect and strictly control e-commerce purchasing activities and impose strict sanctions on online sales fraud.

Increase public awareness of the disadvantages/advantages of online shopping; establish and maintain channels to receive and handle consumers' feedback on fraudulent behavior in e-commerce and online shopping.

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